

SATISFACTORY

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Data Management Plan

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SATISFACTORY CONSORTIUM

The SatisFactory project consortium is composed of:		
CERTH ¹	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	Greece
SIGMA ²	Sigma Orionis SA	France
FRAUNHOFER	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Foerderung der Angewandten Forschung E.V	Germany
COMAU	Comau SPA	Italy
EPFL	Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne	Switzerland
ISMB	Istituto Superiore Mario Boella sulle tecnologie dell'informazione e delle telecomunicazioni	Italy
ABE	Atlantis Engineering AE	Greece
REGOLA	Regola srl	Italy
SUNLIGHT	Systems Sunlight Industrial & Commercial Company of Defensive, Energy, Electronic and Telecommunication Systems S.A.	Greece
GlassUP	GlassUp srl	Italy
Q-PLAN	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL Ltd	Greece

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¹ Project Coordinator

² Partnership terminated on 15/06/16

AUTHORS LIST

Leading Author				
	First Name	Surname	Beneficiary	Contact email
	Anastasia	Matonaki	Q-PLAN	matonaki@qplan.gr
	Kostas	Bougiouklis	Q-PLAN	bougiouklis@qplan.gr
Co-authors				
#	First Name	Surname	Beneficiary	Contact email
1	Pietro Alberto	Cultrona	COMAU	pietro.cultrona@comau.com
2	Dimosthenis	Ioannidis	CERTH	djoannid@iti.gr
3	Ifigeneia	Metaxa	ATLANTIS	metaxa@abe.gr
4	Symeon	Parcharidis	SUNLIGHT	s.parcharidis@sunlight.gr
5	Daniele	Radogna	REGOLA	d.radogna@regola.it
6	Francesco	Sottile	ISMB	sottile@ismb.it

REVIEWERS LIST

List of Reviewers				
#	First Name	Surname	Beneficiary	Contact email
1	Stelios	Krinidis	CERTH	krinidis@iti.gr
2	Evdoxia Irini	Lithoxoidou	CERTH	elithoxo@iti.gr
3	Dimitra	Triantafyllou	CERTH	dtriant@iti.gr

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
PAKE	Password-authenticated key agreement
RAID	Redundant array of independent disks
RFID	Radio-frequency identification
SOP	Standard operating procedure
SRP	Secure Remote Password
UWB	Ultra-wideband, a radio technology
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
DB	Database

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (H2020).

It consists the third version of the project's Data Management Plan (DMP). This version presents in more detail the various datasets that will be produced by the project, describing the main exploitation perspectives for each of them, as well as the major management principles the project will implement around them. It also presents the specifications of the dedicated Data Management Portal developed by the project in the context of the Open Research Data Pilot, allowing the efficient management of the project's datasets and providing proper open access on them for further analysis and reuse.

1. INTRODUCTION

The SatisFactory project aims to enhance and enrich the manufacturing working environment towards attractive factories of the future that encompass key enabling technologies, such as augmented reality, wearable and ubiquitous computing, as well as and customised social communication platforms, coupled with experience design and gamification techniques for the efficient transfer of knowledge and experience among employees.

The purpose of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is to provide an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy that will be used by the consortium with regard to all the datasets that will be generated by the project. The DMP is not a fixed document, but will evolve during the lifespan of the project. This third version of the DMP includes an updated overview of the datasets to be produced by the project, their characteristics and their management processes.

The activities of the SatisFactory project concerning the data management are planned as follows:

- M6: Preliminary analysis and production of the first version of the Data Management Plan (submitted M6);
- M12: Refined analysis based on the progress in the development of the tools and the definition of the case studies, described in the second version of the Data Management Plan;
- M16: Writing of the specifications for the project Data Management Portal (included in this document);
- M17-M19: Development of the Data Management Portal (carried out by CERTH);
- M20: the Data Management Portal is operational;
- M24: Third version of the Data Management Plan, describing procedures implemented by the project in the pilot demonstrators, and preparing the sustainability of the data storage after the end of the project;
- M36: Final Data Management Plan, reflecting on the lessons learnt through the project, and describing the plans implemented by SatisFactory for sustainable storage and accessibility of the data.

Figure 1 - Data management timeline

2. DATASET LIST

All SatisFactory partners have identified and later updated the data that will be produced in the different project activities. The datasets list is provided in the table below, while the nature and details for each dataset are presented in the next section. The datasets added in this version of the report are marked with “new M24”, while the updated with “updated M24”.

This list, although updated, is still indicative and allows estimating the data that SatisFactory will produce – it may be adapted (addition/removal of datasets) in the final version of the DMP to account for the progress of the project activities.

Table 1 - Datasets tracking

#	Dataset Name	Status
1	DS.CERTH.01.IncidentDetection	“updated M24”
2	DS.CERTH.02.ProcessField	
3	DS.COMAU.01.Accelerometer_jacket	“updated M24”
4	DS.COMAU.01.Gyroscope_jacket	“updated M24”
5	DS.COMAU.01.Cardio_jacket	“updated M24”
6	DS.COMAU.01.Temp_jacket	“updated M24”
7	DS.COMAU.02.RFID_torque_wrench	“updated M24”
8	DS.COMAU.03.Work_bench_camera	“updated M24”
9	DS.COMAU.04.Glasses_Accelerometer	
10	DS.COMAU.04.Glasses_Gyroscope	
11	DS.COMAU.04.Glasses_Indoor_pos	
12	DS.COMAU.04.Glasses_temp	
13	DS.COMAU.04.Glasses_camera	
14	DS.COMAU.05.Digital_caliper_USB	“updated M24”
15	DS.COMAU.06.Torque_wrench_USB	“updated M24”
16	DS.COMAU.07.Dinamometer_USB	“updated M24”
17	DS.COMAU.08.Micrometer_USB	“updated M24”
18	DS.COMAU.09.Digital_dial_USB	“updated M24”
19	DS.ISMB.01.FallDetection ((previously named	“updated M24”

	DS.ISMB.01.incidentDetection)	
20	DS.ISMB.02.GestureDetection	“new M24”
21	DS.ISMB.03.PresenceDetection	“new M24”
22	DS.ISMB.04.VideoRecordingEvent	“new M24”
23	DS.ISMB.05.VideoRecording	“new M24”
24	DS.ISMB.06.LocalizationManager_VirtualFencing (previously named DS.ISMB.06.UWB_VirtualFencing)	“updated M24”
25	DS.ISMB.07.UWB_Localization	“new M24”
26	DS.ATLANTIS.1.IntegratedDSS	“updated M24”
27	DS.FIT.01.UserRequirements	
28	DS.Regola.01.ARModels	
29	DS.Regola.02.TrainingData	“new M24”
30	DS.Sunlight.01.MotiveBatteriesAssembly	
31	DS.Sunlight.02.Training&SuggestionsPlatform	
32	DS.Sunlight.03.TempMonitoringInJarFormation	
33	DS.Sunlight.04.MalfunctionIncidentManagement	

The following datasets have been removed from the above list, since finally they were not used and stored in practice:

- DS.Sunlight.05.ClimateMonitorAndControl
- DS.Sunlight.06.WaterConductivityMonitor
- DS.ISMB.02.CameraBased_VirtualFencing
- DS.ISMB.01.VirtualFencing

3. GENERAL PRINCIPLES

3.1 PARTICIPATION IN THE PILOT ON OPEN RESEARCH DATA

SatisFactory participates in the Pilot on Open Research Data launched by the European Commission along with the Horizon2020 programme. The consortium believes firmly in the concepts of open science, and the large potential benefits the European innovation and economy can draw from allowing reusing data at a larger scale. Therefore, all data produced by the project may be published with open access – though this objective will obviously need to be balanced with other important principles described below.

3.2 IPR MANAGEMENT AND SECURITY

As an innovation action close to the market, SatisFactory covers high-TRL technologies and aims at developing marketable solutions. The project consortium includes many partners from the private sector, in particular technology developers (namely Atlantis, GlassUp, and Regola) and end-users (namely COMAU and SUNLIGHT). Those partners obviously have Intellectual Property Rights on their technologies and data, on which their economic sustainability is at stake. Consequently, the SatisFactory consortium will protect that data and crosscheck with the concerned partners before every data publication.

Considering the above, as well as the fact that the data collected through SatisFactory are of high value, every measure should be taken to prevent them from leak or being hacked. This is another key aspect of SatisFactory data management, and therefore, every data repository used by the project will be effectively protected. A holistic security approach will be followed, in order to protect the pillars of information security (confidentiality, integrity, availability).

Security measures will include the implementation of PAKE protocols, such as the SRP protocol, and protection from bots such as CAPTCHA technologies. Moreover, the industrial demo sites apply monitored and controlled procedures related to the data collection, their integrity and protection. The data protection and assurance of privacy of personal information will include protective measures against infiltration, as well as physical protection of core parts of the systems and access control measures.

3.3 PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION

SatisFactory's activities involve the human factor, as the pilots are conducted in real shop floors with actual workers. For some of the activities to be carried out by the project, it may be necessary to collect basic personal data (e.g. name, background, contact details), even though the project will avoid collecting such data unless really necessary. This data will be protected in accordance with the EU's *Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC*³ "on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of

³ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31995L0046&from=en>

such data". National legislations applicable to the project will also be strictly applied, such as the *Italian Personal Data Protection Code*⁴. The industrial pilot sites also implement health and safety management standards (BS OHSAS 18001:2007).

Any personal data, or data directly related to shop floor workers, will be collected after providing the individuals with full details on the experiments to be conducted, and obtaining a signed informed consent form from them.

⁴ <http://www.privacy.it/privacycode-en.html>

4. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

DS.CERTH.01.IncidentDetection	
Data Identification	
Data set description	<p>Dataset for incident detection, along with high-level activities and business processes monitoring (e.g. activities occurring at the shop-floor, etc.), obtained with thermal and depth cameras mounted at specific locations in the shop-floor.</p> <p>In particular, depth cameras will detect the following incidents: 1) human falls, 2) falling items, 3) collisions between moving objects, 4) intrusions to forbidden areas, while thermal cameras will detect overheated areas within the shopfloor.</p> <p>The depth and thermal images will be processed and not saved anywhere, while only the metadata of the incident detection process will be stored. These data will be comprised by anonymized alarms that will include the type of the occurring incident (e.g. human fall, collision, sudden heating of an electrical component etc.) accompanied by the corresponding timestamp and exact location of the event (specific room and exact coordinates on the architectural map of the building). Similar information (metadata of the processed depth and thermal images) do not exist or provided freeware for shop-floor environments.</p>
Source (e.g. which device?)	The dataset will be collected using thermal and depth cameras located at the areas under interest.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	The device will be owned by the industrial plant (CERTH/CPERI, COMAU, SUNLIGHT), where the data collection is going to be performed.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	CERTH
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	CERTH
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	CERTH
WPs and tasks	The data are going to be collected within activities of WP3 and more specifically within activities of T3.3 and T4.3.
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	<p>The dataset will be accompanied by a detailed documentation of its contents. Indicative metadata include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • description of the experimental setup (e.g. location, date, etc.) and procedure that led to the generation of the dataset; • annotated incident, activity, business process, state of the monitored activity and the involved humans per time interval, etc.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The data will be stored at XML format (CIDEM compatible) and are estimated to be 35 MB per day.

Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	<p>The collected data will be used for the development of the activities analysis and incident detection methods of the SatisFactory project and all the tasks, activities and methods that are related to it.</p> <p>Furthermore, the different parts of the dataset could be useful in the benchmarking of a series of human detection and tracking methods, activity detection focusing either on pose and gestures analysis and tracking, on high-level activity recognition, on affect related human activity analysis and on incident analysis and detection.</p>
Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public	<p>The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it.</p> <p>Furthermore, if the dataset or specific portions of it (e.g. metadata, statistics, etc.) are decided to become of widely open access, a data management portal will be created that should provide a description of the dataset and link to a download section. Of course, these data will be anonymized, so as not to have any potential ethical issues with their publication and dissemination.</p>
Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)	<p>The full dataset will be shared with the consortium using a data management portal that created and maintained by CERTH. The public version of the data will be shared within the portal as well. Of course, the data management portal will be equipped with authentication mechanisms, so as to handle the identity of the persons/organizations that download them, as well as the purpose and the use of the downloaded dataset.</p>
Embargo periods (if any)	None
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?	<p>Both full and public versions of the dataset will be accommodated at the data management portal created and maintained by CERTH, while links to the portal will exist at the SatisFactory website. Furthermore, in order to avoid data losses, RAID and other common backup mechanism will be utilized ensuring data reliability and performance improvement.</p> <p>The dataset will remain at the data management portal for the whole project duration, as well as for at least 2 years after the end of the project. The volume of data is estimated to be about 10 GB for all pilots.</p> <p>Finally, after the end of the project, the portal is going to be accommodated with other portals at the same server, so as to minimize the needed costs for its maintenance.</p>

DS.CERTH.02.ProcessField	
Data Identification	
Data set description	<p>Dataset for shop-floor information related to the status and condition of the involved machinery and production-process system (e.g. field data related to the status of a device, such as a pump, a motor etc.) that workers interact with at the shop-floor, etc.).</p> <p>The dataset will also include the human actions and the logging of commands and activity during different conditions and states, to be used for the decision support system and procedures. The dataset will include real-time data and archived historical data of the involved process plants.</p> <p>Similar raw information at the detail level that the project needs, neither exist nor are provided freeware in the literature for shop-floor environments.</p>
Source (e.g. which device?)	The dataset will be collected through the automation systems that acquire the signals from the respective field network of interest. The device managers will communicate with the automation systems in order to transfer the selected data to the Satisfactory repository.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	The device will be owned by CERTH/CPERI, where the data collection is going to be performed.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	CERTH
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	CERTH
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	CERTH
WPs and tasks	Initially the static and persistent data along with a set of dynamic data will be collected within activities of WP3 and more specifically within activities of T3.3 and T3.5. The dynamic data will be updated during WP5 and more specifically in T5.3.
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	<p>The dataset will be accompanied with the respective documentation of its contents. Indicative metadata include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> description of the experimental setup (e.g. process system, date, etc.) and procedure which is related to the dataset (e.g. proactive maintenance action, unplanned event, nominal operation. etc.), scenario related procedures, state of the monitored activity and involved workers, involved system etc.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The data will be stored in XML format and are estimated to be 200-1000 MB per month.

Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	<p>The raw field layer data will be enriched with semantics by the middleware components and will be used for the sharing of information between the process system and the involved actors at the shop-floor.</p> <p>The collected data will be used by the integrated decision support system and the event manager, in order to represent the input for the operation and the maintenance procedures, along with the identification of unplanned incidents at the shop-floor and to analyze the response and behavior of the workers through their interaction with the Satisfactory platform.</p> <p>The initial set of dynamic data will be analyzed during the development of the Satisfactory platform and the nominal dynamic data will be used during the deployment phase at the shop-floor.</p>
Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public	<p>The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it. Furthermore, if specific portions of it (e.g. metadata, statistics, etc.) are to become of widely open access, a data management portal will be created that should provide a description of the dataset and link to a download section. Of course these data will be anonymized, so as not to have any potential correlation and identification of the ethical issues with their publication and dissemination.</p>
Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)	<p>The created dataset will be shared with the consortium using a data management portal created and maintained by CERTH. The public version of the data will be shared within the portal as well. Of course, the data management portal will be equipped with authentication mechanisms, so as to handle the identity of the persons/organizations that download them, as well as the purpose and the use of the downloaded dataset.</p>
Embargo periods (if any)	None
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?	<p>Both full and public versions of the dataset will be accommodated at the data management portal created and maintained by CERTH, while links to the portal will exist at the SatisFactory website. Furthermore, in order to avoid data losses, RAID and other common backup mechanism will be utilized ensuring data reliability and performance improvement. The archiving system of CERTH/CPERI will contain the initial data as sent to the Satisfactory repository.</p> <p>The dataset will remain at the data management portal for the whole project duration, as well as for at least 2 years after the end of the project.</p> <p>The volume of data is estimated to be about 50 GB for all pilots.</p> <p>Finally, after the end of the project, the portal is going to be accommodated with other portals at the same server, so as to minimize the needed costs for its maintenance.</p>

DS.COMAU.01.Jacket	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Data for ergonomic parameters monitoring, coming from sensors installed on a jacket worn by the operators. This dataset will comprise several distinct sub-datasets corresponding to each type of sensor, in order to simplify its maintainability. Those sub-datasets, named DSCOMAU.01.Accelerometer_jacket, DSCOMAU.01.Gyroscope_jacket, DS.COMAU.01.Cardio_jacket etc., will follow similar procedures but will be managed independently.
Source (e.g. which device?)	The dataset will be collected by different sensors installed on jackets worn by operators, namely: an accelerometer, a gyroscope, and a temperature sensor.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	COMAU
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	COMAU with ISMB
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	ISMB
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	ISMB
WPs and tasks	The data are going to be collected within activities of WP3 and WP4.
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Indicative metadata include worker's posture, e.g., trunk bending forward/backward and time stamp.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The data format has not been defined yet. Approximately, the estimated volume of data is less than 2MB per day per worker. Format will be defined by the technical partners.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	Benchmarking of a series of human detection and tracking methods, activity detection focusing either on pose and gestures analysis and tracking

<p>Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public</p>	<p>The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it. Furthermore, if the dataset or specific portions of it (e.g. metadata, statistics, etc.) are to become of widely open access, a data management portal will be created that should provide a description of the dataset and link to a download section. Of course, these data will be anonymized, so as not to have any potential ethical issues with their publication and dissemination.</p>
<p>Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)</p>	<p>The created dataset could be shared by using open APIs through the middleware.</p>
<p>Embargo periods (if any)</p>	<p>None</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)</p>	
<p>Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?</p>	<p>All information belongs to the industrial partner that owns the shop floor. All data will respect the partner policies. Data has to be stored on a SQL Circular Database (not yet existing) that must contain data for at least 1 year, and then each day the oldest data (today-365) should be deleted.</p>

DS.COMAU.02.RFID_torque_wrench	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Sensors installed on the workbench where the operator normally works
Source (e.g. which device?)	RFID installed on the torque wrenches used by the operator.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	COMAU
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	COMAU with REGOLA
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	REGOLA
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	REGOLA
WPs and tasks	The data are going to be collected within activities of WP3 and WP4
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Metadata is yet to be defined by the solution provider.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	Format will be defined by the technical partners. Thus, a data volume estimation will be later provided.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production process recognition and help during the different production phases, avoiding mistakes • Support of quality checks and production batches recalls

<p>Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public</p>	<p>The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it. Furthermore, if the dataset or specific portions of it (e.g. metadata, statistics, etc.) are to become of widely open access, a data management portal will be created that should provide a description of the dataset and link to a download section. Of course, these data will be anonymized, so as not to have any potential ethical issues with their publication and dissemination.</p>
<p>Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)</p>	<p>The sharing of this data is yet to be decided in accordance to COMAU policies and other partners' requirements.</p>
<p>Embargo periods (if any)</p>	<p>None</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)</p>	
<p>Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?</p>	<p>All information belongs to the industrial partner that owns the shop floor. All data will respect the partner policies. Data has to be stored on a SQL Circular Database (not yet existing) till the end of life/warranty of the produced component.</p>

DS.COMAU.03.Work_bench_camera	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Sensors installed on the workbench where the operator normally works
Source (e.g. which device?)	Camera installed on the workbench where the operator works. The type of camera will be defined at a later stage based on the use-cases to be developed.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	REGOLA
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	COMAU with REGOLA
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	REGOLA
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	REGOLA
WPs and tasks	The data are going to be collected within activities of WP3 and WP4
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Metadata is yet to be defined by the solution provider.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	Format will be defined by the technical partners. Thus, a data volume estimation will be later provided.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production process recognition and help during the different production phases, avoiding mistakes • Support of quality checks and production batches recalls

<p>Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public</p>	<p>The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it. Furthermore, if the dataset or specific portions of it (e.g. metadata, statistics, etc.) are to become of widely open access, a data management portal will be created that should provide a description of the dataset and link to a download section. Of course, these data will be anonymized, so as not to have any potential ethical issues with their publication and dissemination.</p>
<p>Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)</p>	<p>The sharing of this data is yet to be decided in accordance to COMAU policies and other partners' requirements.</p>
<p>Embargo periods (if any)</p>	<p>None</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)</p>	
<p>Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?</p>	<p>All information belongs to the industrial partner that owns the shop floor. All data will respect the partner policies. Data has to be stored on a SQL Circular Database (not yet existing) till the end of life/warranty of the produced component.</p>

DS.COMAU.04.Glasses	
Data Identification	
Data set description	<p>The data collected by the sensors installed on the glasses developed by GlassUp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The output data from the Thermal Camera, such as images and time • The output data from the Accelerometer, such as the movement and speed of the glasses at a certain time • The output data from the Gyroscope, such as the acceleration and time • The output data from the Temperature Sensor, such as the temperature detected in front of the glasses over time • The output data from the Light Sensor, such as the brightness of the ambient light in front of the glasses over time • The output data from the Video, such as the videos of the scene in front of the glasses over time <p>Such data are in very large quantity, and mainly do not have any use after the immediate consumption, while especially the cameras' output will be not be stored. They will be processed and then they will be discarded.</p>
Source (e.g. which device?)	<p>The dataset will be collected by different sensors installed on the GlassUp glasses worn by operators, namely: an accelerometer, a gyroscope, an indoor localisation sensor, a temperature sensor, and a camera.</p>
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	GLASSUP
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	COMAU with GLASSUP
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	Middleware Manager with GLASSUP
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	Middleware Manager with GLASSUP
WPs and tasks	The data are going to be collected within activities of WP3 and WP4
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	<p>The dataset will be accompanied by a detailed documentation of its contents. Indicative metadata include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • description of the experimental setup (e.g. location, date and time, serial number of the eyeglass, badge number of the user, code number of the test that was being performed etc.) and procedure that led to the generation of the dataset, • action that the operator will take using the mobile application (i.e. recording video, sending pictures, tag

	the log of date for the event + information/description of the event).
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The data will be stored in XML format and are not estimated yet, being dependent on the video format and the test on uses cases. At least 1GB/day is expected.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benchmarking of a series of human detection and tracking methods, activity detection focusing either on pose and gestures analysis and tracking • For the cameras: Support for contextual data related on the machine/devices monitored, remote support for maintenance
Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public	The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it. Furthermore, if the dataset or specific portions of it (e.g. metadata, statistics, etc.) are to become of widely open access, a data management portal will be created that should provide a description of the dataset and link to a download section. Of course, these data will be anonymized, so as not to have any potential ethical issues with their publication and dissemination.
Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)	The sharing of this data is yet to be decided in accordance to COMAU policies and other partners' requirements.
Embargo periods (if any)	None
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?	<p>The data will be stored daily on the mobile app and will be daily backed up on the server of the Satisfactory. Furthermore, in order to avoid data losses, RAID and other common backup mechanism will be utilized ensuring data reliability and performance improvement.</p> <p>The dataset will remain at the data management portal for the whole project duration, as well as at least for 2 years after the end of the project.</p> <p>Finally, after the end of the project, the portal is going to be accommodated with other portals at the same server, so as to minimize the needed costs for its maintenance.</p>

DS.COMAU.05.Digital_caliper_USB	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Sensors installed on the workbench where the operator normally works
Source (e.g. which device?)	RFID installed on the torque wrenches used by the operator.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	COMAU
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	COMAU with REGOLA
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	REGOLA
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	REGOLA
WPs and tasks	The data are going to be collected within activities of WP3 and WP4
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Metadata is yet to be defined by the solution provider.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	Format will be defined by the technical partners. Thus, a data volume estimation will be later provided.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production process recognition and help during the different production phases, avoiding mistakes • Support of quality checks and production batches recalls

<p>Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public</p>	<p>The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it. Furthermore, if the dataset or specific portions of it (e.g. metadata, statistics, etc.) are to become of widely open access, a data management portal will be created that should provide a description of the dataset and link to a download section. Of course, these data will be anonymized, so as not to have any potential ethical issues with their publication and dissemination.</p>
<p>Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)</p>	<p>The sharing of this data is yet to be decided in accordance to COMAU policies and other partners' requirements.</p>
<p>Embargo periods (if any)</p>	<p>None</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)</p>	
<p>Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?</p>	<p>All information belongs to the industrial partner that owns the shop floor. All data will respect the partner policies. Data has to be stored on a SQL Circular Database (not yet existing) till the end of life/warranty of the produced component.</p>

DS.COMAU.06.Torque_wrench_USB	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Sensors installed on the workbench where the operator normally works
Source (e.g. which device?)	RFID installed on the torque wrenches used by the operator.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	COMAU
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	COMAU with REGOLA
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	REGOLA
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	REGOLA
WPs and tasks	The data are going to be collected within activities of WP3 and WP4
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	It will be defined by the technical partners, thus a data volume estimation will be later provided.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The data format has not been defined yet.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production process recognition and help during the different production phases, avoiding mistakes • Support of quality checks and production batches recalls

<p>Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public</p>	<p>The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it. Furthermore, if the dataset or specific portions of it (e.g. metadata, statistics, etc.) are to become of widely open access, a data management portal will be created that should provide a description of the dataset and link to a download section. Of course, these data will be anonymized, so as not to have any potential ethical issues with their publication and dissemination.</p>
<p>Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)</p>	<p>The sharing of this data is yet to be decided in accordance to COMAU policies and other partners' requirements.</p>
<p>Embargo periods (if any)</p>	<p>None</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)</p>	
<p>Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?</p>	<p>All information belongs to the industrial partner that owns the shop floor. All data will respect the partner policies. Data has to be stored on a SQL Circular Database (not yet existing) till the end of life/warranty of the produced component.</p>

DS.COMAU.07.Dinamometer_USB	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Sensors installed on the workbench where the operator normally works
Source (e.g. which device?)	RFID installed on the torque wrenches used by the operator.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	COMAU
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	COMAU with REGOLA
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	REGOLA
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	REGOLA
WPs and tasks	The data are going to be collected within activities of WP3 and WP4
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Metadata is yet to be defined by the solution provider.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The data format has not been defined yet, it will be defined by the technical partners , thus a data volume estimation will be later provided.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production process recognition and help during the different production phases, avoiding mistakes • Support of quality checks and production batches recalls

<p>Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public</p>	<p>The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it. Furthermore, if the dataset or specific portions of it (e.g. metadata, statistics, etc.) are to become of widely open access, a data management portal will be created that should provide a description of the dataset and link to a download section. Of course, these data will be anonymized, so as not to have any potential ethical issues with their publication and dissemination.</p>
<p>Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)</p>	<p>The sharing of this data is yet to be decided in accordance to COMAU policies and other partners' requirements.</p>
<p>Embargo periods (if any)</p>	<p>None</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)</p>	
<p>Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?</p>	<p>All information belongs to the industrial partner that owns the shop floor. All data will respect the partner policies. Data has to be stored on a SQL Circular Database (not yet existing) till the end of life/warranty of the produced component.</p>

DS.COMAU.08.Micrometer_USB	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Sensors installed on the workbench where the operator normally works
Source (e.g. which device?)	RFID installed on the torque wrenches used by the operator.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	COMAU
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	COMAU with REGOLA
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	REGOLA
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	REGOLA
WPs and tasks	The data are going to be collected within activities of WP3 and WP4.
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Metadata is yet to be defined by the solution provider.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The data format has not been defined yet. It will be defined by the technical partners, thus a data volume estimation will be later provided.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	Production process recognition and help during the different production phases, avoiding mistakes.

<p>Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public</p>	<p>The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it. Furthermore, if the dataset or specific portions of it (e.g. metadata, statistics, etc.) are to become of widely open access, a data management portal will be created that should provide a description of the dataset and link to a download section. Of course, these data will be anonymized, so as not to have any potential ethical issues with their publication and dissemination.</p>
<p>Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)</p>	<p>The sharing of this data is yet to be decided in accordance to COMAU policies and other partners' requirements.</p>
<p>Embargo periods (if any)</p>	<p>None</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)</p>	
<p>Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?</p>	<p>All information belongs to the industrial partner that owns the shop floor. All data will respect the partner policies. Data has to be stored on a SQL Circular Database (not yet existing) till the end of life/warranty of the produced component.</p>

DS.COMAU.09.Digital_dial_USB	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Sensors installed on the workbench where the operator normally works
Source (e.g. which device?)	RFID installed on the torque wrenches used by the operator.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	COMAU
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	COMAU with REGOLA
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	REGOLA
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	REGOLA
WPs and tasks	The data are going to be collected within activities of WP3 and WP4.
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Metadata is yet to be defined by the solution provider.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The data format has not been defined yet. It will be defined by the technical partners, thus a data volume estimation will be later provided.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production process recognition and help during the different production phases, avoiding mistakes • Support of quality checks and production batches recalls

<p>Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public</p>	<p>The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it. Furthermore, if the dataset or specific portions of it (e.g. metadata, statistics, etc.) are to become of widely open access, a data management portal will be created that should provide a description of the dataset and link to a download section. Of course, these data will be anonymized, so as not to have any potential ethical issues with their publication and dissemination.</p>
<p>Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)</p>	<p>The sharing of this data is yet to be decided in accordance to COMAU policies and other partners' requirements.</p>
<p>Embargo periods (if any)</p>	<p>None</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)</p>	
<p>Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?</p>	<p>All information belongs to the industrial partner that owns the shop floor. All data will respect the partner policies. Data has to be stored on a SQL Circular Database (not yet existing) till the end of life/warranty of the produced component.</p>

DS.ISMB.01.FallDetection	
Data Identification	
Data set description	This dataset contains information about Smart Assembly Station workers fall events. The information is obtained by Gesture & Content Recognition Manager performing a complex set of analysis on input video streams from a composite device, including a conventional colour camera and a time-of-flight infrared sensor.
Source (e.g. which device?)	Gesture & Content Recognition Manager connected to a Kinect XBOX 360 depth sensor located in the Smart Assembly Station
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	Devices are owned by the industrial partner.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	ISMB
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	ISMB
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	CERTH
WPs and tasks	WP3: T3.3
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	The fall dataset includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the identifiers of both Smart Assembly Station and shop floor where the event occurred the date when the event occurred
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The dataset XML format is defined by the Common Information Data Exchange Model XML Schema Definition (see WorkAlertInformationType). Each dataset is normally less than 1MB.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The event triggered is used by SatisFactory ecosystem components to improve actors reaction times in safety related situations and to activate procedures to avoid recurrence of accidents.
Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public	All information belongs to the industrial partner that owns the shop floor. All data will respect the partner policies.

Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)	The dataset is distributed using the LinkSmart middleware MQTT broker.
Embargo periods (if any)	None
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?	The information is stored by CERTH Common Information Data Exchange Model for the whole project duration.

DS.ISMB.02.GestureDetection	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Through a continuous monitoring of the Smart Assembly Station the Gesture & Content Recognition Manager can spot predefined worker gestures. This dataset contains information about the detected gestures.
Source (e.g. which device?)	Gesture & Content Recognition Manager connected to a Kinect XBOX 360 depth sensor located in the Smart Assembly Station.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	Devices are owned by the industrial partner.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	ISMB
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	ISMB
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	CERTH
WPs and tasks	WP3: T3.3
Standards	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation? 	The gesture data set include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the identifiers of both Smart Assembly Station and shop floor where the event occurred the date when the event occurred the type of gestures (LeftHandSwipeRight, RightHandSwipeLeft, BothHandsRaised)
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The dataset XML format is defined by the Common Information Data Exchange Model XML Schema Definition (see GestureType). Each dataset is normally less than 1MB.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	Stored data can be used to feed management toolkits, and to manage contactless applications where users don't have easy access to standard input devices due to safety gear.
Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public	All information belongs to the industrial partner that owns the shop floor. All data will respect the partner policies.
Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)	The dataset is distributed using the LinkSmart middleware MQTT broker.
Embargo periods (if any)	None
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?	The information is stored by CERTH Common Information Data Exchange Model for the whole project duration.

DS.ISMB.03.PresenceDetection	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Through a continuous monitoring of the Smart Assembly Station the Gesture & Content Recognition Manager can spot worker presence. This dataset contains information about the number of workers detected.
Source (e.g. which device?)	Gesture & Content Recognition Manager connected to a Kinect XBOX 360 depth sensor located in the Smart Assembly Station.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	Devices are owned by the industrial partner.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	ISMB
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	ISMB
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	CERTH
WPs and tasks	WP3: T3.3
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	The presence data set include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the identifiers of both Smart Assembly Station and shop floor where the event occurred • the date when the event occurred • the people count and previous people count
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The data set XML format is defined by the Common Information Data Exchange Model XML Schema Definition (see PresenceType). Each data set is normally less than 1MB.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	Stored data can be used to monitor the Smart Assembly Station usage.
Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public	All information belongs to the industrial partner that owns the shop floor. All data will respect the partner policies.
Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)	The dataset is distributed using the LinkSmart middleware MQTT broker.
Embargo periods (if any)	None
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?	The information is stored by CERTH Common Information Data Exchange Model for the whole project duration.

DS.ISMB.04.VideoRecordingEvent	
Data Identification	
Data set description	When specific events such as fall alarms are triggered by the Gesture & Content Recognition Manager, the Multiple Media Manager server encodes automatically the video and uploads it to the central unit. The data set gives information about the current phase of the encoding process.
Source (e.g. which device?)	Multiple Media Manager installed on Smart Assembly Station core hardware (in current deployment an Intel Next Unit of Computing)
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	Devices are owned by the industrial partner.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	ISMB
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	ISMB
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	CERTH
WPs and tasks	WP3: T3.3
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	The video recording data set include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the identifiers of both Smart Assembly Station and shop floor where the event occurred • the date when the event occurred • the referred alert event id • the path of the produced video • the information of the current phase about the encoding process
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The data set XML format is defined by the Common Information Data Exchange Model XML Schema Definition (see RecordingType). Each data set is normally less than 2MB.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	Stored data can be used by the supervisor to correctly retrieve stored video information.
Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public	All information belongs to the industrial partner that owns the shop floor. All data will respect the partner policies.
Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)	The dataset is distributed using the LinkSmart middleware MQTT broker.
Embargo periods (if any)	None
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?	The information is stored by CERTH Common Information Data Exchange Model for the whole project duration.

DS.ISMB.05.VideoRecording	
Data Identification	
Data set description	When specific events such as fall alarms are triggered by the Gesture & Content Recognition Manager, the Multiple Media Manager server encodes automatically the video and uploads it to the central unit. The data set is the encoded video containing the recording of the last minutes before the fall event.
Source (e.g. which device?)	Multiple Media Manager installed on Smart Assembly Station core hardware (in current deployment an Intel Next Unit of Computing)
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	Devices are owned by the industrial partner.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	ISMB
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	ISMB
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	ISMB
WPs and tasks	WP3: T3.3
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	The video contained in the data set is enriched using auxiliary data from the Gesture & Content Recognition Manager.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The videos in the dataset have the following characteristic: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MP4 format • H264 video encoding • Overlay metadata
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The data could allow the visual detection and isolation of specific conditions and factors which could have contributed to an incident in order to address the necessary actions to avoid its recurrence. Furthermore, the data analysis can provide mechanisms to search for incident occurred previously in similar circumstances (e.g. workers without protective equipment or with the same skills or at the same process time) to measure the effects of

	preventive procedures.
Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public	All information belongs to the industrial partner that owns the shop floor. All data will respect the partner policies.
Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)	The videos are distributed by the Multiple Media Manager Central Unit using HTTPS progressive download.
Embargo periods (if any)	None
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?	The video are stored by the Multiple Media Manager Central Unit for a configurable period of time (currently 150 days)

DS.ISMB.04.LocalizationManager_VirtualFencing	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Dataset reporting potential incidents based on workers location in the shop floor. A virtual fencing approach based on a point in polygon algorithm is adopted. The localization manager detects whether a worker is approaching a dangerous area or whether he/she is inside of it. In addition, it reports also whether there is no more the potential incident.
Source (e.g. which device?)	The localization data is sent by an UWB GW device. The UWB GW receives estimated positions of workers from UWB-based wearable devices carried by them.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	The developed software will be owned by ISMB whilst the stored data will be owned by the industrial partners.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	Industrial partners (CERTH, SUNLIGHT, COMAU)
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	ISMB
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	CERTH
WPs and tasks	The data are going to be collected within activities of WP3 and more specifically within activities of T3.3.
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Indicative metadata include: Worker Id, state of the worker (e.g., inside or outside a dangerous area), name of the dangerous area, current location of the worker in relative or absolute coordinates, alert Id, and time stamp.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The geofencing events can be accessed through MQTT APIs. The data is XML formatted and it is compliant with the CIDEM specifications. The volume of data generated per worker depends on the number of incidents detected. One single event generates 2 KB of data.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The collected data will be used for the development of the proactive incident detection functionalities of the SatisFactory platform.

<p>Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public</p>	<p>The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it. Furthermore, if the dataset or specific portions of it (e.g. metadata, statistics, etc.) are to become of widely open access, these could be shared through the Localization Manager. Of course, the data will be anonymized, so as not to have any potential ethical issues with their publication and dissemination.</p>
<p>Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)</p>	<p>The LocalizationManager VirtualFencing dataset could be shared using the MQTT APIs of the Localization Manager component for debugging, demonstration and management purposes. The public version of the data could be shared through the Localization Manager by using a suitable authentication mechanism, so as to handle the identity of the persons/organizations that access them.</p>
<p>Embargo periods (if any)</p>	<p>None</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)</p>	
<p>Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?</p>	<p>Data will be stored in the CIDEM by the LinkSmart middleware. This is done by means of the event aggregator. Typically, the Localization Manager software will be installed in the end-users' premises for the industrial pilot demonstrators.</p>

DS.ISMB.07.UWB_Localization	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Dataset reporting, in real-time, the current position of workers at the shop floor by means on UWB-based wearable devices. In particular, a wearable device continuously performs ranging (i.e. distance) measurements from fixed UWB anchors, at the shop floor, and estimates the worker position running a localization algorithm.
Source (e.g. which device?)	The raw localization data will be estimated by the UWB-based wearable devices which are carried by the workers. The wearable devices send the workers location to an UWB GW which is connected with the SatisFactory infrastructure.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	The UWB-based wearable devices will be owned by ISMB. In particular, ISMB is going to develop wearable devices compliant with the IEEE802.15.4a standard.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	Industrial partners (CERTH, SUNLIGHT, COMAU)
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	ISMB
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	CERTH
WPs and tasks	The data are going to be collected within activities of WP3 and more specifically within activities of T3.3.
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Indicative metadata include: Worker Id, wearable battery level, estimated position of the worker in relative or absolute coordinates, shop floor Id, estimated position flag, anchor connectivity, number of collected ranging measurements, accuracy of localization, time stamp, and packet data number.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The localization data will be stored in the CIDEM by the LinkSmart middleware, if it is necessary. The data is currently formatted in JSON. In order to be compliant with the CIDEM, the final format will be XML. For each worker, there are estimated three positions per second. The volume of data generated depends on the number of workers that are localized. One single event generates 1 KB of data.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The collected data will be used by the Localization Manager for the detection of proactive incidents at the shop floor, based on current workers position. Furthermore, localization data can be exploited by other components of SatisFactory infrastructure such as Augmented Reality and Collaboration Tools.

<p>Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public</p>	<p>The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it. Furthermore, if the dataset or specific portions of it (e.g. metadata, statistics, etc.) are to become of widely open access, these could be shared through the UWB GW. Of course, these data will be anonymized, so as not to have any potential ethical issues with their publication and dissemination.</p>
<p>Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)</p>	<p>The UWB Localization dataset could be shared using the MQTT APIs of the UWB GW for debugging, demonstration and management purposes. The public version of the data could be shared through the UWB GW by using a suitable authentication mechanism so as to handle the identity of the persons/organizations that access them.</p>
<p>Embargo periods (if any)</p>	<p>None</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)</p>	
<p>Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?</p>	<p>Data will be stored in the CIDEM, if it is requested, by the LinkSmart middleware. This is done by means of the event aggregator. Typically, the UWB infrastructure (i.e. UWB GW, UWB anchor nodes, UWB-based wearable devices) will be installed in the end-users' premises for the industrial pilot demonstrators.</p>

DS.ATLANTIS.01.IntegratedDSS	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Dataset for shopfloor feedback engine obtained by Smart Sensor Network and Thermal and Optical Sensors (i.e. cameras, their type will be defined at a later stage), made available through Device Manager, together with data stemming from Incident Management Tools as well as the Gamification Adaptation Interface
Source (e.g. which device?)	Device Manager, Event Manager, Semantic Context Manager, AR In-Factory Platform, Gamification Adaptation Interface
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	The device will be owned by the industry (COMAU, CERTH/CPERI, SUNLIGHT), where the data collection is going to be performed.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	Various partners related to the specific incident and/or operation
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	Various partners related to the specific incident and/or operation
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	ATLANTIS will store data related to integratedDSS (various partners can handle the rest of the data)
WPs and tasks	The data are going to be collected within activities of WP3 and WP4 and WP5
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Indicative metadata include: shop floor data, production results (including timestamp, location), recommendations for maintenance and manufacturing operations, recommendations derived from the gamification adaptation interface.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	Data can be available in XML or JSON format. Estimation of the volume of data cannot be predicted in advance of a real use of the technology at the shop floor level.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The collected data will be used for better understanding of the processes and activities evolving in the Shopfloor which in conjunction with pre-defined response policies and strategies will provide actionable knowledge in the form of a set of recommendations regarding both maintenance and manufacturing operations. Also, new knowledge will be extracted and exploited from the Gamification Adaptation Interface. This knowledge comes from the social collaboration of workers outside the working environment.
Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public	The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it.

Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)	The sharing of this data is yet to be decided along with the industrial partners.
Embargo periods (if any)	None
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?	Data will be stored in a DB. RAID and other common backup mechanism will be utilized to ensure data reliability and performance improvement and to avoid data losses.

DS.Regola.01.ARModels	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Dataset containing information captured at low-level and representing human activities in the shop floor context; graphic model describing objects processed during the activities; video and audio recorded during actions (e.g. activities occurring at the shop-floor, etc.) obtained with AR cameras mounted on specific wearable devices; executable script containing step-by-step instructions, dynamic help visualized through the glasses, etc.
Source (e.g. which device?)	The dataset will be collected using cameras integrated in the wearable device and cameras located at the areas of interest. The recordings will be colour and HR.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	The device will be owned by the industry (COMAU, CERTH/CPERI, SUNLIGHT), where the data collection is going to be performed.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	Regola
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	Regola
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	Regola
WPs and tasks	The data are going to be collected within activities of T2.5 and of T4.3.
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	The dataset will be accompanied by a detailed documentation of its contents. Indicative metadata include: (a) description of the working phase (e.g. location, date, etc.) SOP and procedure that led to the generation of the dataset, (b) description of involved objects.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	3D Formats: 3DM, 3DS, DXF, DWG, IGES, Collada DAE, FBX, OBJ, PLY, ASC, RAW, SKP, SLDPRD, STP, STEP, STL, WRL, VRML, SGF e SGP (proprietary scenegraph file formats). Image Formats: BMP, DIB, JPG, TGA, PNG, DDS, HDR Audio Formats: WAV, MID, MP3 Video Formats: AVP, MPG Motion Capture Formats: BVH, C3D, HTR, GTR Original SOP Formats: PDF, DOCX, XLS, XLSX, etc. R3D RT SOP Formats: RTS (proprietary XML-Based file format). The data will be stored at XML format and are estimated to be 40 GB per day.
Data exploitation and sharing	

Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The collected data will be used for analysis of operator's behaviour and the development of the scripts containing step-by-step instruction and the controls of correctness of activities.
Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public	The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it. Furthermore, if the dataset or specific portions of it (e.g. metadata, statistics, etc.) are to become of widely open access, a data management portal will be created that should provide a description of the dataset and link to a download section. Of course, these data will be anonymized, so as not to have any potential ethical issues with their publication and dissemination.
Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)	The full dataset will be shared using a data management portal. The data management portal will be equipped with authentication mechanisms, so as to handle the identity of the persons/organizations that download them, as well as the purpose and the use of the downloaded dataset.
Embargo periods (if any)	None
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?	Both full and public versions of the dataset will be accommodated at the data management portal; RAID and other common backup mechanism will be utilized ensuring data reliability and performance improvement.

DS.Regola.02.TrainingData	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Dataset containing audit data captured by the Presentation Tool. The dataset includes execution instances of the Training Procedures in the shop floor context. The data are described in the Annex B of the deliverable: D2.5. They are parameters identifying the trainee and the procedure; the procedure under execution; the time spent for the execution of the procedure's steps; the survey data submitted at the end of the procedure; etc.
Source (e.g. which device?)	The dataset will be collected using the platform where the Presentation tool is under execution: Smartphones; Smartglass; Tablets.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	The device will be owned by the industry (COMAU, CERTH/CPERI, SUNLIGHT), where the data collection is going to be performed.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	Regola
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	ABE
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	The industry (COMAU, CERTH/CPERI, SUNLIGHT), where the data collection is going to be performed.
WPs and tasks	The data are going to be collected within activities of T2.5.
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	The dataset is stored in XML format, so the metadata specifying it are already part of the dataset.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The dataset is stored in XML format. The overall volume of the data depends on the amount of training sessions completed. A possible value could be compute ad: $10Kb * N$, where N is the number of training sessions.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The collected data will be used for further analysis by the Training Data Analytics Tool currently under development by ABE. The aim of the analysis is to assess the skills of the trainee and to gather training statistics, in order to provide feedback able to improve the training procedures.

<p>Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public</p>	<p>The full dataset will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access on it. If the dataset or portions of it are going to become of widely open access, the data must be anonymized, in order to avoid A) privacy issues, according to the applicable laws of the country where the data are gathered, B) issues with the trade unions.</p>
<p>Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)</p>	<p>The dataset is not intended to be shared using a data management portal; instead, it is intended to be managed by the Training Data Analytics tool. Nevertheless, the dataset could be easily accessed / reused for further applicable needs, taking in account how easily statistics about working steps could be built from the bulk of the individual data gathered.</p>
<p>Embargo periods (if any)</p>	<p>None</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)</p>	
<p>Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?</p>	<p>The dataset will be stored in the CIDEM. The data lifetime is determined by the applicable policies specified by the shop floors.</p>

DS.Sunlight.01.MotiveBatteriesAssembly	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Technical data for battery assembly and working instructions for assembly and quality control.
Source (e.g. which device?)	Technical data for battery assembly will be provided from SAP. Working instructions will be available from a database which will be accessed through the internal company network.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	Sunlight will be the owner of the device.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	CERTH
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	CERTH
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	SUNLIGHT/CERTH
WPs and tasks	Data will be collected for WP3, T3.4
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Metadata that will be used are SAP codes, order numbers and drawing numbers.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The data will be in text format including drawings and photos. The estimated total volume will not exceed 1TB.
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The data will be used only for the development of the Satisfactory application.
Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public	Data will be confidential. Data that cannot be shared because it includes Customer order details and technical know-how details.
Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)	Data cannot be shared.
Embargo periods (if any)	None
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?	Data are stored in SAP but an intermediate storage unit will be used in order to avoid data loses and provide a data backup.

DS.Sunlight.02.Training&SuggestionsPlatform	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Battery assembly training data (e.g. assembly instructions, drawings, quality check instructions, procedures etc.)
Source (e.g. which device?)	Data are stored in an internal database which will be accessed through internal LAN
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	Sunlight will be the owner of the device.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	CERTH/FIT
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	CERTH/FIT
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	SUNLIGHT/CERTH/FIT
WPs and tasks	Data will be collected for WP3, T3.3 and T3.4
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Metadata that will be used are battery assembly procedures and instructions, assembly drawings.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The data will be in text format
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The data will be used only for the development of the Satisfactory application.
Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public	Data will be confidential because it includes technical know-how details.
Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)	Data will be shared by using a data management portal.
Embargo periods (if any)	None
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?	Data are stored in a storage device of a server or computer. A back up will be stored in an external storage device.

DS.Sunlight.03.TempMonitoringInJarFormation	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Battery Temperature measurements
Source (e.g. which device?)	Thermal cameras
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	Sunlight will be the owner of the device.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	CERTH/FIT
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	CERTH/FIT
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	SUNLIGHT/CERTH/FIT
WPs and tasks	Data will be collected for WP3, T3.3
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Metadata that will be used are production dates and the Jar formation equipment code number.
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The data will be in text format
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The data will be used only for the development of the Satisfactory application.
Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public	Data will be available only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services
Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)	Data will be shared by using a data management portal.
Embargo periods (if any)	None
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?	Data will be stored in the storage device of the developed system (computer). A back up will be stored in an external storage device.

DS.Sunlight.04.MalfunctionIncidentManagement	
Data Identification	
Data set description	Malfunction Incidents
Source (e.g. which device?)	Malfunction Incidents are logged manually in xls file
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device	Sunlight will be the owner of the device.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	ATLANTIS
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	ATLANTIS
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	SUNLIGHT/ATLANTIS
WPs and tasks	Data will be collected for WP3, T3.5
Standards	
Info about metadata (Production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Metadata that will be used are the incident details (date, hour, place, etc.)
Standards, Format, Estimated volume of data	The data will be in text format
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The data will be used only for the development of the Satisfactory application.
Data access policy / Dissemination level (Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) / Public	Data will be available only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services
Data sharing, re-use and distribution (How?)	Data will be shared by using a data management portal.
Embargo periods (if any)	None
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup): where? For how long?	Data will be stored in the storage device of the developed system (computer). A back up will be stored in an external storage device.

5. DATA MANAGEMENT PORTAL

This section provides an analysis with regards to the specifications of the SatisFactory Data Management Portal, a web based portal, developed within the SatisFactory project for the purposes of the management of the various datasets that will be produced by the project, as well as, for supporting the exploitation perspectives for each of those datasets.

Based on the information provided in the previous sections, the Data Management Portal needs to manage a large number of datasets, collected by various devices, such as sensors and cameras, but also manually inserted in IT systems and collected through direct interactions with employees (e.g. interviews).

Furthermore, the Data Management Portal will need to be flexible in terms of the parts of datasets that are made publicly available. Special attention is going to be given on ensuring that the data made publicly available violates neither IPR issues related to the project partners, nor the regulations and good practices around personal data protection. For this latter point, systematic anonymization of personal data will be made.

5.1 DATA MANAGEMENT PORTAL FUNCTIONALITIES

The DMP offers a variety of functionalities in order to facilitate the management of the data produced within the purposes of the SatisFactory Project.

The Data Management Portal is implemented through a **web based platform** which enables its users to easily access and effectively manage the various datasets created throughout the development of the project. The portal **is connected to the SatisFactory datasets**, as stored in CIDEM, through the CIDEM API (RESTful services) providing access to static (i.e. shop floor gbXML), as well as dynamic (i.e. Events) information.

Regarding the **user authentication**, as well as the respective permissions and access rights, the following three user categories are foreseen:

- **Admin**
The Admin has access to all of the datasets and the functionalities offered by the DMP and is able to determine and adjust the editing/access rights of the registered members and users (open access area). Finally, the Admin is able to access and extract the analytics, concerning the visitors of the portal.
- **Member**
When someone successfully registers to the portal and is given access permission by the Admin, she/he is then considered as a “registered Member”. All the registered members will have access to and be able to manage most of the collected datasets.
- **User**
SatisFactory project is dedicated to knowledge sharing and for this reason, it aims at providing a platform for the assessment of project outcomes and the publication of material related to the understanding of smart factory environments. As a result, apart from the admin and the registered members areas, an open access area will be

available for users who will not need to register and they will have access to some specific datasets, as well as to project outcomes (e.g. demo datasets).

Figure 2 - Login Page of the Data Management Portal

Each dataset available in the DPM is accompanied by a short description. The users are able to download the datasets in specific formats (e.g. xml, csv, etc.) for further analysis. Security measures will be applied to avoid data exposure (e.g. CAPTCHA technologies).

Data Management			
INTRODUCTION	DATA	CHARTS	
DOCUMENTS	DATASETS		
Title	Description	Uploaded	
B2MML Standard	B2MML Standard structure that has been i...	19/09/2016 13:46	GET IT!
Gamification Standard	Gamification Standard structure that has...	19/09/2016 13:55	GET IT!
gbXML Standard	gbXML Standard structure that has been i...	19/09/2016 13:47	GET IT!
OpenSocial Standard	OpenSocial Standard structure that has b...	19/09/2016 13:54	GET IT!
R3D Standard	AR tools Operational Procedures structur...	19/09/2016 13:50	GET IT!

Figure 3 - Data access page of the Data Management Portal

Great emphasis will be given on properly visualizing the various data collected within the project, so that the members can easily and effectively manage them. A variety of graphs, pie charts etc. is going to be employed for helping members to easily understand and elaborate the data.

5.2 DATA MANAGEMENT PORTAL ARCHITECTURE & DESIGN

Architecture

The overall system architecture is shown in the figure below, presenting all individual interfaces developed for the Data Management Portal, in a 3-tier schema (database layer, application layer, client layer) where each layer performs a specific function.

Figure 4 - Data Management Portal Architecture

Data Tier

The Data Tier includes the databases, the data management tools (CIDEM), as well as the data access layer that encapsulates the recovery mechanisms for historical data (CIDEM API). Through an Application Programming Interface (API), the methods of data storage management are exposed to the Application Tier, ensuring robust communication and continuous unobtrusive data flow.

Application Tier

The Application Tier checks the functionality of an application by performing detailed editing. It constitutes the intermediate level and also the heart of the analysis tool for extracting useful knowledge. It should be noted that this level goes beyond simply presenting the data but mainly into processing and analysing them (parallel simulation scenarios implementation), towards extracting a variety of useful and meaningful indicators and graphs.

Client Tier

This is the highest level of the application, with which the end user interacts via the user interface elements. The way of presenting the information is very important, given that the tool will be used by people who may not be familiar with technology. In this context, the development of the application is designed in such a way that ensures the user-friendliness and quick adaptation to the end-users.

6. CONCLUSION

The third version of this report on the SatisFactory Data Management Plan provides an updated overview of the data produced by the project and of the challenges and constraints that need to be taken into account for managing it. In addition, it describes the updated procedures, as well as the infrastructure implemented by the project to efficiently manage the produced data. In particular, it includes the overview and specifications of one of the key tools specially implemented for managing the project's data, namely the SatisFactory Data Management Portal.

The Data Management Portal needs to manage a large number of datasets, collected by various means, i.e. sensors, cameras, manual inputs in IT systems and direct interactions with employees (e.g. interviews). Nearly all the project partners will be owners or/and producers of data. Similarly, all the technical work packages of the project will produce data – though the majority will be produced within WP3. Thus, the Data Management Portal provides proper access/edit rights to all the project partners.

The SatisFactory Data Management Plan also puts a strong emphasis on the appropriate collection – and publication if allowed – of metadata, storing all the information necessary for the optimal use and reuse of the produced datasets. This metadata will be managed by each data producer and will be integrated in the Data Management Portal.

Finally, the Data Management Portal needs to be flexible regarding the parts of the datasets that are made publicly available. Particular attention will be paid on ensuring that the data made openly available violates neither IPR of the project partners, nor the regulations and good practices around personal data protection. For this latter point, systematic anonymization of personal data will be made.

The SatisFactory Data Management Plan is a dynamic document, updated throughout the whole project lifecycle. The final version of this report will be delivered by the end of the project, reflecting on lessons learnt and describing the plans implemented for sustainable storage and accessibility of the data, even beyond the project's duration.